

THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING IN TWO DIFFERENT AGES (CHILDHOOD AND ADOLESCENCE)

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Annotation. This thesis shows that the age is an essential factor that influences language learning. The differences on language acquisition and ultimate proficiency in childhood and adolescent period are studied exploring some scholars' research works.

Key words. Language acquisition, adolescent, childhood, maturity, lexical diversity, immersion, accent, language awareness.

Аннотация. Этот тезис показывает, что возраст является важным фактором, влияющим на изучение языка. Различия в овладении языком и его конечном владении в детском и подростковом периоде изучаются на основе исследовательских работ некоторых ученых.

Ключевые слова. Овладение языком, подростковый возраст, детство, зрелость, лексическое разнообразие, погружение, акцент, языковое осознание.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis yosh tilni o'rganishga ta'sir qiluvchi muhim omil ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Bolalik va o'smirlik davridagi til o'zlashtirish va yakuniy malakadagi farqlar ayrim olimlarning tadqiqot ishlarida o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Tilni o'zlashtirish, o'smirlik, bolalik, yetuklik, leksik xilma-xillik, immersiya, urg'u, tilni bilish.

The study of age effects on second language acquisition has been explored and reached various valuable results. The conducted researches show that the instructional methods and acquiring a language are different between young and adult learners. Researches connect learners' metalinguistic awareness to their schooling. According to Singleton and Pfenninger (2018), the age is not always a factor that effects on acquisition: exposure, language instruction and native-like environment. Second language is acquired for education, employment, or an official or social language in a particular country. Second language acquisition can be any language acquisition after acquiring a native language. The ages of L2 learners are important for second language acquisition. Johnson and Newport (1989)'s two interpretations based on Lenneberg's Critical Period Hypothesis

show differences between age-related acquisition: Exercise Hypothesis (states learner's capacity for acquiring a language through continuous exercises on language learning and this ability will remain intact through the whole life or if not, a decline or disappearance of learning language ability can happen during maturational period) and Maturation Hypothesis (states disappearance or decline of capability of acquiring language with maturation naturally). The latter has age effects on L2 acquisition. It is used age-appropriate instructional methods for children, adolescent, and adults because they have different experience, cognitive ability and maturity.

Childhood period. Early language learners are engaged in pre-school programs that are specialized to make language learning easy. Because children look like “sponges” that they are eager to absorb language and literalization of language features (Munoz, 2019). According to Lenneberg (1967), in order to gain native-like performance in fluency, language acquisition must be occur before puberty. Penfield and Roberts (1959) consider that first ten years of life is the optimum period of acquiring a language. According to Singleton (1989), learners who begin to learn second language in their early age are more likely to reach higher levels of success in language proficiency, particularly pronunciation and grammar in comparison with those who begins in later life. According to Llanes and Munoz (2013), children's rate of learning language in SA context is advantageous and accelerated than other ages by the immersion situation. Children outperform adults in gaining foreign accent when they are exposed to SA setting being able to communicate with native speakers. However, Harley's study shows that older immersion learner are more successful in comparison with the younger one. Childhood does not mean to grow physically, but it is also considered as the period of mental development. According to Cook (2012), students who acquire a language in formal circumstances cannot be at the same process with those who acquire languages in natural environment. But children are learners who acquire linguistic and social knowledge simultaneously. Children acquire a language easily and a natural way which is less anxious than that of adolescents or adults do. The best way to learn a new language for children is to hear the target language being spoken regularly. According to Sun (2015), children benefit when they are provided with language exposure and usage rather than with input-limited instructional classes. Games, visual or aural stories and also interesting and colorful instructional materials are useful tools for child language acquisition. At this stage, external motivation sources are teachers, parents or caregivers, peers, people in surroundings, and mass media

(particularly cartoons and interesting short films). Early starters are easily motivated and encouraged with external rewards when they perform well. As it is difficult to hold their attention, interesting class should be organized with the help of attentive instructions (picture cards). According to Nikolay and Djigunovich (2006), instructions provided in classroom should be designed with opportunities that are provided in natural SLA in order to reach attainment in children's language acquisition in foreign language context. Early starters are taught only repetition of structures to make sentences (*I have a dog, I have a ball, I have a cat*). Moreover, in order to widen a set of lexicon knowledge, childhood is important period. Because vocabulary learned in childhood is recalled and used in oral conversation easily. This can be enhanced by practicing drills and imitations, so they are able to pronounce easily. In the period of childhood, the age of 6 and 7, almost all phonological features and important rules are acquired fully (Kerswill, 1996). The young are better learners in morphosyntax and pronunciation skills. Despite their slower rate in the beginning of learning, children have high achievement in long term (Munoz, 2019). Children have less affective-liter when acquiring a new language rather than adults. Because they are not afraid of making mistakes. Larson-Hall (2008) and Dwaik Shehadeh (2015)'s study shows early starters achievement in auditory perception and in reading respectively, but not listening, grammar, writing after short-term instructions.

Adolescence. According to Munoz et al. (2010), in comparison with children, formal settings which give clear instruction and assessment tests is beneficial for both adolescents and adults and school instructions more closely match their capability than it does those of younger students. Grammar is intentionally acquired by adolescents and adults with the help of explicit instructions. Deductive grammar instruction which gives specific rules and examples of how to use, is beneficial to adolescents. Language learning of adolescents is influenced by maturation, neurocognitive development, and affective-factors. Teenagers are experienced enough to comprehend and they are able to produce conversation, apply methods in their learning, and they have potential goals why they are learning a language which is led by intrinsic motivation. Adolescents enjoy experiencing a teacher's authority that means teacher should act as a lecturer, guide and director. According to Nikolov and Djigunovic (2006), every child is not ready for language learning because of some lack specific cognitive skills but adolescents and adults acquire language using their problem-solving skills and experience in their native languages.

When it comes to phonology, age-related decline occurs through the years passed. Adolescents whose arrival was after 12 years old, showed less native-like performance but child arrivals under 12 had (Munoz, 2019). In spite of having advantages of learning language in childhood, the young tend to mix their L1 and L2. Adolescents are quick learner and they outperform children and adults in syntax and listening skills. For adolescents, instructional classes and teachers can be a source of language. They can improve their ability in language learning by listening to various sources, challenging themselves in beyond their level materials consciously. Adolescents see more advantages in receiving comprehensible input, retaining word in memory and expressing themselves rather than children. Age-related decline occurs in morphological domain and syntax domain (Johnson & Newport, 1991) after puberty. This means there is the loss in linguistic features at the age of adolescents and adults despite some outperformance and this is explained by Maturational State Hypothesis.

In conclusion, learners are not differentiated merely by their ages, but culture and backgrounds has a great influence on second language acquisition. Munoz (2014b) stated about time spent abroad and current informal contact as the best predictors of fluency, lexical diversity and accuracy when examining oral performance of SLLs. Moreover, the initial rate of acquisition and ultimate level of attainment are performed differently in different age groups. The former shows how rapidly different aged learners learn a language, the latter highlights native-like attainments achieved in second language acquisition.

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